

Data-centric Service-Based Architecture for Edge-Native 6G Network

Gabriele Baldoni^{*†}, José Quevedo[‡], Carlos Guimarães^{*}, Antonio de la Oliva[†] and Angelo Corsaro^{*}

^{*}ZettaScale Technology, France

[†]Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Spain

[‡]Instituto de Telecomunicações, Portugal

Abstract—Starting with 5G, mobile networks moved away from the point-to-point model used by previous generations towards a Service-Based Architecture (SBA) focused on a Cloud-native design. While 5G considers the SBA mainly as a central location with a single administrative domain, 6G is expected to become more of a fully-distributed system. This raises the need for flexible service routing capabilities that allow the utilization of the distributed resources available over multiple infrastructures. This paper embraces this vision and explores the utilization of data-centric and dataflow mechanisms for a seamless realization and interaction of composable services in a fully distributed Edge-native 6G architecture. The feasibility and suitability of this vision are showcased through a proof-of-concept prototype, validated over selected 5G workflows using different technologies, with results demonstrating the advantages of pursuing data-centric and dataflow approaches.

Index Terms—6G, SBA, Data-Centric, Dataflow, Distributed Systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

5G networks introduced a key disruption into its architectural design, the Service Based Architecture (SBA), which departed from point-to-point interactions between 3GPP Network Functions (NFs) to embrace standard service Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). This concept allowed modular and Cloud-native approaches to be adopted into the core network where a given NF exposes and uses services from any other function in the network. Although the SBA introduced a giant leap in terms of extensibility and scalability of the network, it remains a host-centric approach, which is not suited for distributed and decentralized NF communication due to the need for mapping function addresses to service names. Improvements in this area, introduced by e.g. the Service Communication Proxy (SCP) in Release 16, have not demonstrated clear benefits. Moreover, 6G research is also considering the optimization of the SBA model to extend End-to-End (E2E) orchestration to the Far-Edge domain, including the adoption of serverless computing. The SBA will then become the communication kernel (also commonly referred to data fabric) of any E2E 6G system, easing the implementation of self-sustained functions, network scalability, efficient exposure of network capabilities, automation, flexibility to new deployments, and simplification of the architecture. Nevertheless, a streamlined and seamless integration of capabilities and services anywhere in the Cloud-to-Far-Edge continuum (hereinafter, referred solely as continuum) is required to abstract

the inherent complexity of a heterogeneous, distributed, and eventually volatile infrastructure.

To this end, a better balance between NF granularity and the number of required interactions between the rest of the system is required, so that NFs can be added, updated, and replaced in a flexible and modular manner. The idea is to minimize the number of NFs involved in the different procedures by aggregating common ones into atomic functions (i.e., aggregating radio-related functions). Thus, it will be possible to reduce today's 5G functional dependencies that create long sequential procedures with several variants. Novel networking protocols that adequately support a rising adoption of Edge and ubiquitous computing are required to (i) fulfill the 6G promises (e.g., “zero delay”); (ii) facilitate efficient virtualization of NFs over the Core and Edge computing resources; and (iii) enable hyper-distributed and decentralized deployments. Moreover, the accuracy and consistency of data are introducing new requirements for data management procedures. Both aspects are paramount to overcoming the complexity and scalability issues, mostly due to coordination barriers between communication and computing, already witnessed in 5G [1].

To efficiently tackle such an approach in the 6G architecture, the foundation of the underlying SBA must be rethought from scratch without ties to any particular communication architecture. Data-centric networking (DCN) [2] appears as a more suitable networking model, instead of today's host-centric model, to better fulfill the requirements of an Edge-Native 6G networks' SBA. By combining data-centric and dataflow concepts, 6G networks can evolve into dynamic chains of serverless, loosely coupled, and stateless atomic NFs, dynamically orchestrated to achieve an optimal balance between consumed and available resources across the continuum. This concept will prove to be essential to support a *Network of Networks* framework vision [3], and to provide enhanced connectivity and services in a variety of use-cases, such as Public Protection and Disaster Relief (PPDR) scenarios [4] where the 6G fabric must adapt to extreme performance and global service coverage requirements but only when such communications are in place.

In this work, we present the foundations for a data-centric interaction, modeled as a dataflow, of serverless atomic functions as the redesign of current control-plane core network concepts and procedures. The theory is then put into practice by exploring concrete realizations of the data-centric and dataflow ideas by implementing them in a proof-of-concept

prototype and validating them over selected 5G workflows. The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section II analyzes existing state-of-the-art. Section III introduces the envisioned concept of a novel Data-centric Service-Based Architecture for Edge-Native 6G networks, highlighting its architectural decisions, and benefits. The experimental validation of selected 5G workflows is presented in Section IV. Finally, conclusions are drawn and suggestions made for future work in Section V.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

This section overviews existing efforts to evolve today's 5G SBA and to adopt dataflow models in 5G service composability, emphasizing still open challenges to be tackled in upcoming 6G networks.

A. Service-Based Architecture

In Release 15, 3GPP defined a common control protocol (e.g., HTTP) to implement two communication models for the interactions among NFs through the SBA: (i) request-response; or (ii) subscribe-notify. Communications between NFs can be either direct, using the Network Repository Function (NRF) for discovery purposes, or, starting from Release 16, mediated by the SCP, which enables centralized signaling monitoring and decouples the discovery and selection procedures.

However, while the SCP provides better control over service routing, it has not brought any clear benefit, mainly because of two factors. First, while the SCP facilitates the implementation of the SBA in a highly distributed Edge scenario, it still acts as a single entry point for a cluster of NFs. Thus, it is intrinsically centralized, not only representing a single point of failure but also introducing a scaling and latency bottleneck point. Second, while the SBA is a step in the right direction toward a microservice-based architecture, it falls short to match the levels of distribution, decentralization, and atomicity envisioned for the 6G systems. In particular, the 5G control plane (unlike what would be expected from its successor) is still highly contained and centralized thus favoring the direct interaction between NFs. Another approach widely used in the Cloud-native ecosystem is the service mesh, which is a dedicated infrastructure facilitating service-to-service communications between services or microservices using chains of proxies.

The most promising path to address the aforementioned issues, as already identified by 3GPP in Release 18, is to adopt data-centric solutions for the SBA and to leverage its name-based routing capabilities. In [5], a deployment example for the SCP is provided, where a name-based routing mechanism provides IP over Information-Centric Networking (ICN) capabilities. However, a centralized communication node - Service-Router - is still required, which acts as the rendezvous point to establish the path between both NFs. Also, since it transports IP-over-ICN, it might prove to be inefficient or create unnecessary overhead, although it has the potential to provide a more seamless integration within current 5G systems. Other approaches to transparently embed the SCP as part of the SBA realization are also underway, avoiding NFs from being

explicitly designed and configured to use the SCP [6]. In [7], a novel solution based on Software-Defined Networking (SDN) for interconnecting NFs is proposed as an alternative to the SCP. Since the SDN controller handles the policies internally, NFs do not need to include additional parameters in service interaction, allowing transparent communication.

B. Dataflow Service Composability

Data Flow Programming (DFP) [8] is a computational model that represents application as a directed graph, where each node of the application graph, called an *operator*, is a computational unit, and the directed arcs between them are unbounded *First-In-First-Out* (FIFO) streams, called *links*. Operators are executed concurrently and triggered following different strategies, e.g., all inputs (i.e., links that flow towards a node) need to be present, or only a subset of them. Naturally, this computational model has been widely adopted for network workloads. It is leveraged to provide serverless, fast, and cost-effective unified stream and batch data processing, paving the way for fully managed data processing services that are easily provisioned, managed, and scaled. Moreover, it eases the decomposition model of services into microservices, which provides several advantages in terms of not only resiliency, scalability, and composability but also flexibility, maintainability, performance, and security.

Its application to 5G networks is still limited and mainly targets supporting mechanisms. In [9], dataflow is used to implement Cloud Radio Access Network (C-RAN) workloads (e.g., Channel Estimation, Inversion, and Equalization) in a platform-agnostic, scalable, and programmable way. In [10], it is used for intelligent network management, implementing an N-MAPE-K (Network Monitor-Analyze-Plan-Execute over a shared Knowledge) as a way to simplify the execution of each component: (i) collect data from the network; (ii) analyze the data, leveraging AI/ML algorithms; (iii) plan network management actions; and (iv) execute the planned actions. Finally, [11] analyses the impact of distinct decomposition models for NFs on the attack surface of the system, applying the derived service decomposition models on 5G NRF.

Although the evolution for a data-centric SBA and higher decomposition of core NFs are already underway, they are being tackled independently. This paper explores dataflow-based service composability as an enabler for the seamless integration of these isolated approaches, thus promoting innovation and customization to meet the requirements of emerging applications and services while providing simpler and more convenient approaches for programmers, operators, and service providers.

III. DATA-CENTRIC SERVICE-BASED ARCHITECTURE FOR EDGE-NATIVE 6G NETWORK

The principles behind the proposed Data-centric Service-Based Architecture for Edge-Native 6G Network are presented in this section in the form of a system architecture, as depicted in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Data-centric Service-Based Architecture for Edge-Native 6G Network overview

A. A Layering Approach for a Compositional Vision

The proposed solution is based on a layered architecture that is hierarchical in nature, with each horizontal layer building upon each other. Each layer provides an abstraction to ease the development and management of the overall architecture, paving the way for a system that is flexible, scalable, and able to handle the complex demands of Edge-Native 6G Networks.

1) **Service DataFlow**: The service dataflow approach for service composability facilitates the definition of more complex services (hereinafter referred to as Service Functions) by combining and reusing atomic components into service chains on demand. Moreover, since atomic functions can be serverless and stateless, it allows parallel execution where function instances are executed concurrently as long as their data dependencies are satisfied. By relying on a dataflow programming model, services are represented as a directed graph, stitching and chaining together different atomic components in a similar way to the Network Function Virtualization (NFV) framework.

To do so, this layer creates and manages the interconnection between atomic components across the continuum, which are dynamically established and isolated upon the instantiation of the Service Function. Such interconnections are configured in the underlying Data-Centric Service Routing in order to create a distributed location-transparent communication bus. The service dataflow automatically generates and configures unique names and mapping between such names and Service Function inputs and outputs. This layer is also responsible for the lifecycle management of not only the entire Service Functions but also each atomic component. It includes tasks like bin-packing, orchestration, and scheduling, thus determining the most resource-efficient way to place atomic components across the continuum, as well as instantiation, termination, and monitoring.

2) **Data-centric Service Routing**: Enabling the communication between dynamic, possible volatile, atomic functions as well as the optimal selection of redundant functions pose a major challenge to the service routing layer. It is widely recognized that the Internet architecture is sub-optimal for addressing this sort of challenge, and novel paradigms such as ICN have been emerging and introduced at different levels. While the adoption of these technologies as a full replacement

for the underlying Internet Architecture has proven to be harsh, its application in contained environments to address specific challenges has been increasingly studied.

By relying on a data-centric, naturally distributed, approach, the realization of the communication bus for service routing offers location-transparent primitives and allows data to be directly addressed without specifying its origin. In other words, data is retrieved and routed solely based on its name, allowing atomic functions to be developed without the complexity typically associated with endpoint configuration. Such capability becomes essential to support the reuse and/or sharing of atomic functions across different *Service Dataflows*. Also, a Data-centric Service Routing is expected to provide increased performance and efficiency, better scalability, and more robustness as well as reduce network overhead and levels of indirection. This layer receives name-data tuples from the Service DataFlow layer and, based on its configuration, forwards them to interested Atomic Function instances. Furthermore, it automatically establishes links between data-centric entities, either routers or applications.

3) **Atomic Function Instances**: The dynamic and opportunistic realization of Atomic Functions, on top of a set of resources distributed across the continuum, would be at the basis of the stringent performance indicators expected to be fulfilled by the next generations of mobile systems. By splitting NFs into fine-grained building blocks, Atomic Functions can be designed and implemented as serverless and stateless instances, guaranteeing parallelization of operations, non-conflicting access, and control over system resources.

Still, this layer raises challenges at different levels, including the decomposition of high-end services into serverless Atomic Functions, their integration on top of heterogeneous multi-stakeholder distributed resources, and the optimal allocation and scheduling of resources to provide the required assurance at the service level. These elements remain a challenge, being consistently identified in 6G research [12]. Interconnections between the instances, as already mentioned, are defined by the Service DataFlow layer, which abstracts the Data-centric service routing, by providing a DFP-based API to the Atomic Functions. Such abstraction takes care of declaring the interests from an instance towards the Data-centric service routing, thus enabling each Atomic Function to receive and send data.

4) **Distributed Resources**: The resource layer comprises any available physical or virtualized resource spanning across the continuum. Resources are typically organized in a hierarchical and integrated computing infrastructure extending across multiple tiers comprising Clouds and central data centers, Edge data centers in the middle, and Far-Edge computing devices that are available locally in the access area. Each tier of this distributed infrastructure differs in essential properties (e.g., network topology, computing power, volatility, mobility, and how they span across different administrative domains) which is perceived as an adoption barrier. Thus, it requires a degree of abstraction and the necessary tools for streamlined and flexible management that conceals the underlying complexity.

Cloud computing relies on huge, well-interconnected data

centers, based on the latest computing and networking fabrics, providing virtually unlimited resources. The Edge is composed of small data centers based on Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) hardware with metropolitan rings or enterprise network topologies. When reaching the Far-Edge, usually on-premises infrastructures (e.g., under a Public network integrated Non-Public Network architecture - PNI-NPN), the resources become sparse, less powerful, and, eventually, volatile.

B. Architectural Impact and Benefits

The proposed Data-centric SBA for Edge-Native 6G Networks has several architectural impacts and benefits, which are presented below.

1) **Efficient Core Network Signalling:** the data-centric primitives and intrinsic multicast capabilities of the proposed SBA, as well as the atomicity of functions and their composability as dataflow graphs, contribute to more efficient signaling, both from the perspective of faster procedures and lower message overhead. Additionally, it enables parallel signaling surpassing today's sequential signaling, while eliminating the service indirection of discovery processes. Moreover, it allows bundling more functionality together (e.g., for serving a given context), thus reducing the overhead that crosses the network.

2) **Streamline Refactoring:** the location-transparency and the data-oriented primitives of the SBA contribute to shipping software updates more efficiently and effectively, especially with the increased softwarization of distributed nature being considered for 6G networks. The capability to update and/or refactor existing functions, paves the way for rapid innovation cycles by identifying and quickly addressing ways to improve processes, yielding rapid results and, eventually, a reduction in the Total Cost of Ownership (TCO).

3) **Serverless, Stateless, Reusable, and Shareable functions:** by considering Atomic Functions and their composition as a dataflow graph over data-centric primitives, the proposed solution leverages stateless functions that can be shared, and transparently replicated across the continuum in a serverless and dynamic fashion on top of likely volatile resources. Such simpler components are instantiated among different stakeholders (e.g., Internet Service Providers (ISPs), cloud operators, and verticals), facilitating and creating a whole new set of opportunities for the realization of PNI-NPN concepts. Moreover, the intrinsic characteristics of the underlying data-centric communication bus enable seamless reusability of atomic components by multiple service flow realizations (with the proper trade-off between isolation and reutilization).

4) **E2E Orchestration over the Continuum:** the Service DataFlow introduces a new approach for the orchestration of 6G networks, where the management of various heterogeneous software modules is performed in a unified manner while offering finely-grained services across the continuum. Despite this, the orchestration shall provide interfaces for interconnecting multiple administrative domains, promoting the sharing of components and providing a virtually interconnected continuum from private networks at the Far-Edge up to the Cloud.

5) **Security and Fault-Tolerance:** security and fault-tolerance are taken in a multi-layer approach, each tackling

different aspects of the architecture. The Service DataFlow layer provides security and fault-tolerance at the content level, thus providing both properties from an E2E perspective. The Data-centric Service Routing layer focuses on securing the link, thus providing hop-to-hop security, leveraging both TLS and mutual TLS. At the Atomic Function layer, application-specific (e.g. authentication and access control) security is applied. Nevertheless, this approach allows each layer to focus on a different aspect of security, contributing to the onion security model, in which the system security is achieved by layering different layers of secure components.

IV. EVALUATION / ASSESSMENT

A proof-of-concept of the proposed architecture was implemented to validate its design and assess its impact. It focuses on the data-centric principles of the proposed architecture, namely the *Data-centric Service Routing* and *Service Dataflow*. Taking into consideration that 5G networks and the 5G SBA are the best existing approximation of what future communications systems will be like, the proof-of-concept was developed considering selected 5G workflows. For meaningful comparison, the selected procedures represent the different communications models found in today's 5G systems, realized on top of different solutions.

A. Proof-of-Concept Implementation

Zenoh and Zenoh-Flow were selected to implement the proposed approach of a Data-centric SBA for Edge-Native 6G Networks. Both present a unique set of capabilities that make them a perfect fit for the *Data-centric Service Routing* layer and *Service Dataflow*, respectively. Zenoh /zeno/ is a pub/sub/query protocol unifying data in motion, data at rest, and computations. Moreover, it is fully decentralized and provides enhanced capabilities, like the dynamic discovery of nodes, priority, and very low network overhead. Such capabilities have already proven its suitability as communication protocol between edge applications [13]. Zenoh-Flow is a dataflow programming framework that leverages data centrality and location transparency, thus allowing for applications to span across the continuum. It provides a declarative dataflow graph definition, seamless operation across the continuum (including automatic deployment), fosters code reuse by the means of composite operators, and achieves high-performances with low latency and higher throughput. Zenoh-Flow functionalities are already being leveraged as dataflow layer for network intelligence algorithms in the context of automated network management [10].

Open5GS an open-source implementation for 5G Core and Evolved Packet Core (EPC) (Release 17 at the time of writing), was deployed, along with emulated gNBs and User Equipment (UE). This setup was used to gather traces of the selected 5G workflows, which were later used to replay the behavior of the NFs, their reference points, interactions, and exchanged data. This includes not only the proposed solution, but also HTTP, gRPC, Istio, MQTT, and Kafka solutions due to their adoption in today's 5G systems.

Fig. 2: 5G SBA architecture, highlighting the workflows used for evaluation.

The validation has been carried over our internal testbed composed of 3 machines (AMD Ryzen 7 5800X @ 4.0 GHz, 32GB of DDR4 3200MHz RAM, running Ubuntu 20.04 LTS), directly interconnected via 100GbE fiber-based NICs over a ring topology.

B. 5G Workflow Evaluation

The 5G workflows selected for evaluation purposes are: (i) *PDU Session Establishment* [14]; and (ii) *Charging Policy Updates* [15] (both presented in Fig. 2 along their dataflow graphs). These workflows were selected because they cover the different communication models between NFs.

1) *PDU Session Establishment*: This workflow follows a Request/Reply pattern. For this workflow, the proposed solution is compared against (i) HTTP, as the protocol defined in the 3GPP for the 5G SBA communication, (ii) gRPC, a widely used protocol for SBA-based interactions, (iii) and Istio, a widely used open-source service-mesh implementation. Results are shown in Fig. 3 (left subplot), depicting the total time required to complete the entire PDU session establishment exchange. The proposed solution performs one or more orders of magnitude faster than HTTP, gRPC, and

Fig. 3: Workflow completion time for different protocols. (lower is better).

Istio, regardless of service discovery being performed (calls #1 and #3 in Fig. 2). On the one hand, HTTP and gRPC show

similar performance. The reasons lie on (i) a more efficient data exchange; (ii) faster serialization; and (iii) less wire-overhead, thus less transmission time. On the other hand, for the service-mesh implementation, the reason lies in how the service mesh is implemented, consisting of a chain of proxies to provide location transparency, thus increasing overall latency. Moreover, Table I shows that Zenoh also optimizes the wire-overhead by efficiently mapping topic names into integer values, in opposite to the remaining solutions.

2) *Charging Policy Updates*: This workflow follows the Subscribe/Notify pattern. In this scenario, the proposed solution is compared against widely used protocols for publish/subscribe like MQTT and Kafka. Results are shown in Fig. 3 (right subplot), also depicting the total time required to push the notification to subscribed entities. The proposed solution outperforms MQTT and Kafka. By leveraging Zenoh, the proposed solution exploits peer-to-peer communications (thus allowing consuming and producing NFs to communicate directly), while both MQTT and Kafka solutions only offer brokered communications (thus introducing at least one additional hop). As in the previous workflow, Zenoh also presents savings in the wire overhead compared to Kafka and MQTT, as shown in Table I.

TABLE I: Analysis of wire overhead, and lines of code, for the different protocols.

	PDU Session Establishment				Charging Policy Update		
	Proposed Solution	HTTP	Istio	gRPC	Proposed Solution	Kafka	MQTT
Overhead (bytes)	365	738	1130	963	11	128	36
Overhead (%)	8.9	18.0	21.1	63.2	20	232	65
CLOC Count lines of code	408	1664	1960	548	114	198	93

C. Feature Analysis

Table II presents a feature analysis of the evaluated solutions, focusing on the capabilities that are crucial for a decentralized SBA envisioned by 6G networks.

These protocols are divided into three families: (i) host-centric, like HTTP and gRPC, which address the exact endpoint holding the data; (ii) service-centric (also referred as service-mesh), like Istio, which address services themselves regardless of its location; and (iii) data-centric, like Zenoh, Kafka, and MQTT, that address the data itself disregarding its holder. While host-centric solutions fall short when considering decentralized scenarios in which microservices are deployed anywhere in the continuum, service-centric solutions fall short when multiple clusters must be connected across the continuum. Workarounds are usually in place to alleviate the problem (e.g., using middleboxes or communication proxies) at the cost of more complex infrastructure and sub-optimal communications. Instead, data-centric solutions, like the one proposed, allow decoupling and abstracting from the underlying infrastructure, making it a more suitable paradigm for decentralized scenarios.

Moreover, each paradigm is usually tied to a specific communication model. On one side, host-centric and service-centric protocols tend to leverage request/reply, as they are much like to follow the client/server paradigm. On the other side, data-centric protocols either use publish/subscribe or Request/Reply (equivalent to location-transparent Queries), where consumers specify the data they are interested independently of its location and intrinsic multicast capabilities are leveraged. The proposed solution appears as a more sophisticated data-centric solution that blends together publish/subscribe and query-based (Request/Reply) communication models in a single solution.

The dataflow programming model adopted by the proposed solution also enables a streamlined development of core Service Functions. This approach allows developers to focus on the underlying logic of each component without the need to write extensive boilerplate code. The effectiveness of this approach is demonstrated in Table I, which highlights a significant reduction in the number of lines of code (CLOC) required for the implementation of each workflow. In other words, the dataflow programming allows the proposed solution to decompose complex applications into simpler and atomic components, a methodology that bears similarities to the serverless paradigm gaining momentum in the Cloud domain. These are then defined and composed together via declarative approaches while making them aware of exchanged types which abstracts the serialization/deserialization tasks from the developer. Moreover, the associated benefits are expected to have even larger impact as a higher number of (atomic) functions with complex interactions are embraced to realize future communication systems.

In conclusion, the data flow programming and data-centric primitives adopted by the proposed framework will facilitate the task of defining and implementing the different functions of the core network, enabling the development of simpler, more focused interfaces between components.

V. CONCLUSION

This work looks at the evolution of today's 5G SBA to support a flexible service routing and discovery capabilities as well as at a service dataflow layer to simplify the development of Service Functions and to enable full utilization of the distributed resources available over multiple infrastructures across the continuum. Thus, it proposes the utilization of data-centric and dataflow mechanisms toward the seamless realization and interaction of composable services in a fully distributed, Edge-native 6G architecture. To assess the potential and the feasibility of the proposed solution, it was implemented using Zenoh and Zenoh-Flow and evaluated over representative 5G workflows, with results showcasing the benefits in terms of: (i) procedure completion times (between 10 to 100 times faster), (ii) wire overhead (between 2 and 2.5 times smaller, for PDU session establishment, and between 3.5 and 11 times smaller in charging policy update), and (iii) lines of code (up to 4 times lower). Moreover, the impact of the solution is expected to expand beyond the presented KPIs, by introducing a new set of capabilities as part of the data fabric of future 6G

TABLE II: Qualitative analysis of the different protocols.

	Proposed solution	HTTP	gRPC	Istio	Kafka	MQTT
Paradigm	Data-centric	Host-centric	Host-centric	Service-Centric (Intra-Cluster) Host-centric (Inter-Cluster)	Data-centric	Data-centric
Topology	Peer-to-Peer, Brokered, Routed	Peer-to-Peer	Peer-to-peer	Routed	Brokered	Brokered
Communication Model	Query (Request/Reply) Publish/Subscribe (Push / Pull)	Request/Reply	Request / Reply	Request / Reply	Publish/Subscribe (Pull)	Publish/Subscribe (Push)
Types Aware	Yes	Blob	Yes	Blob	Blob	Blob
Composability	Declarative Application Definition	No	No	Declarative Service Definition	No	No

networks that enable higher degrees of flexibility, efficiency, and scalability.

As future work, the proposed solution is going to be further validated against current and future standardization results in existing testbeds, like 5TONIC and 5GAIner, to provide real-deployment insights on the feasibility of a DCN approach for the SBA. Furthermore, an evaluation of the proposed approach shifted to the data-plane is also envisioned, to validate its applicability and efficiency in both recent efforts from 3GPP, in particular, the Edge Applications Service Discovery Function (EASDF), and as the underlying transport for Cloud-native approaches like service-mesh. Such insights will help steer decisions in standardization bodies.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Q. Li *et al.*, “6G Cloud-Native System: Vision, Challenges, Architecture Framework and Enabling Technologies,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 96 602–96 625, 2022.
- [2] O. Serhane, K. Yahyaoui, B. Nour, and H. Mouncla, “A Survey of ICN Content Naming and In-Network Caching in 5G and Beyond Networks,” *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 4081–4104, 2021.
- [3] Z. Zhang *et al.*, “6G Wireless Networks: Vision, Requirements, Architecture, and Key Technologies,” *IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 28–41, 2019.
- [4] L. Militano, A. Arteaga, G. Toffetti, and N. Mitton, “The Cloud-to-Edge-to-IoT Continuum as an Enabler for Search and Rescue Operations,” *Future Internet*, vol. 15, no. 2, 2023.
- [5] 3GPP, “Technical Specification Group Services and System Aspects; System architecture for the 5G System (5GS); Stage 2 (Release 18),” 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), Technical Specification (TS) 23.501, 12 2022, version 18.0.0.
- [6] S. Robitzsch, U. Olvera-Hernandez, J. Costa-Requena, and M. Skarp, “Enabling Service-Oriented Principles for the User Plane of Mobile Telecommunication Networks,” in *2022 IEEE Conference on Standards for Communications and Networking (CSCN)*, 2022, pp. 111–117.
- [7] P. Fondo-Ferreiro, F. Gil-Castineira, F. J. González-Castaño, and D. Candal-Ventureira, “A Software-Defined Networking Solution for Interconnecting Network Functions in Service-Based Architectures,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 19905–19916, 2022.

- [8] W. M. Johnston, J. R. P. Hanna, and R. J. Millar, “Advances in dataflow programming languages,” *ACM Comput. Surv.*, vol. 36, no. 1, pp. 1–34, 2004.
- [9] N. Grigoryan, E. Matus, and G. P. Fettweis, “Df4cran: Dataflow framework for cloud-ran signal processing,” in *2019 IEEE 2nd 5G World Forum (5GWF)*, 2019, pp. 141–147.
- [10] M. Gramaglia *et al.*, “Network intelligence for virtualized ran orchestration: The daemon approach,” in *2022 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit)*, 2022, pp. 482–487.
- [11] S. Behrad, D. Espes, P. Bertin, and C.-T. Phan, “Impacts of Service Decomposition Models on Security Attributes: A Case Study with 5G Network Repository Function,” in *2021 IEEE 7th International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft)*, 2021, pp. 470–476.
- [12] M. A. Uusitalo *et al.*, “6G Vision, Value, Use Cases and Technologies From European 6G Flagship Project Hexa-X,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 160 004–160 020, 2021.
- [13] D. Sabella, *Multi-access Edge Computing: Software Development at the Network Edge*. Springer Cham, 2021.
- [14] 3GPP, “Technical Specification Group Core Network and Terminals; 5G System; Session Management Services; Stage 3 (Release 18),” 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), Technical Specification (TS) 29.502, 12 2022, version 18.1.0.
- [15] —, “Technical Specification Group Core Network and Terminals; 5G System; Session Management Policy Control Service; Stage 3 (Release 18),” 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), Technical Specification (TS) 29.512, 12 2022, version 18.0.0.

BIOGRAPHIES

Gabriele Baldoni (M.Sc.’2017) is a Technologist at ZettaScale Technology, and a PhD student at Universidad Carlos III de Madrid.

José Quevedo (Ph.D.’2020) is a Senior Researcher at Instituto de Telecomunicações and the executive director of the 5GAIner laboratory.

Carlos Guimarães (Ph.D.’2019) is a Senior Technologist at ZettaScale Technology.

Antonio de la Oliva (Ph.D.’2008) is an Associate Professor at Universidad Carlos III Madrid.

Angelo Corsaro (Ph.D.’2003) is CEO/CTO at ZettaScale Technology.